

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Richard D. Semba

Your email address: rdsemba@jhmi.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 24 April 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, writing original draft, writing reviewing & editing, conceptualization, supervision

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

No	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
No	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
No	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
No	From litigation or legal cases
No	From grants
No	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="radio"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input type="radio"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="radio"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="radio"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="radio"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="radio"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="radio"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="radio"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

Richard D. Semba

Notes

(1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.

(2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.

(3) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.

(4) Interests that cannot contractually be declared need not be described in detail, but their existence must be noted. If the contract specifies that not even the presence of a contractual limitation can be declared, the contributor should state they are unable to complete the form.

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Elizabeth Chatpar

Your email address: echatpa1@jh.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29 APR 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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<input type="checkbox"/> From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/> From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/> From litigation or legal cases	<input type="checkbox"/> Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Elizabeth Chopra". The signature is written in a cursive style with a long horizontal stroke at the end.

Notes

(1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Iman Habib

Your email address: ihabib1@jh.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29-04-2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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<input type="checkbox"/> From litigation or legal cases	<input type="checkbox"/> Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

NA

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

NA

Signature

Aman Habib

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Brent F. Kim

Your email address: bkim40@jh.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29-04-2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'B. H. Kou', with a long horizontal line extending to the right.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Elizabeth Sharp

Your email address: esharp6@jh.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 06 25 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology and Writing-Review and Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

None

Signature *Elizabeth Sharp*

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: David C. Love

Your email address: dlove8@jhu.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 22/04/2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology; Writing – Reviewing and Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "David Love". The signature is written in a cursive style with a long, sweeping underline.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Sara Lupolt

Your email address: slupolt1@jhu.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 01/08/2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication? No

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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Non-financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Sam Dupont". The signature is written in a cursive, slightly slanted style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Andrew Thorne-Lyman

Your email address: athorne1@jhu.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 4/22/2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing-Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None reported

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

None reported

Signature

 4/25/2024

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Lori Rosman

Your email address: lrosman@jhmi.edu

Date of completion of form (23 04 2024):

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology – developed search strategies and managed search results Writing – review & editing search methodology

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Joan A. Casey

Your email address: jacasey@uw.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 06/09/2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing — review & editing; Supervision

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'John G. ...', written over a faint, light blue grid background.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Juleen Lam

Your email address: Juleen.Lam@csueastbay.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 22 04 2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing (reviewing and editing)

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'J. J.', written in a cursive style.

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
- (2) Contributors to a research project should declare any interests that a reasonable person would want to be aware of, in order to be confident that all relevant interests are known and can be evaluated for their potential to disrupt or compromise decision-making in the project.
- (3) It is unlikely that someone with no interests in relation to a project would still be interested in being involved in a project. Declaring no interests is therefore unlikely to be a valid response to the questions in this form.
- (4) Interests that cannot contractually be declared need not be described in detail, but their existence must be noted. If the contract specifies that not even the presence of a contractual limitation can be declared, the contributor should state they are unable to complete the form.

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Keeve E. Nachman

Your email address: knachman@jhu.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29/04/2024

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Conceptualization, Supervision, Project Administration

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I have previously conducted research related to the topic of this systematic review. I do not believe that my involvement in that research will compromise my ability to perform the research in a rigorous and ethical manner.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'K. L.', written in a cursive style.

Notes

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